

Measuring and Evoking Curiosity in Statistics/Probability Students (Year 0)

Visruth Srimath Kandali, Amy Truong, Ella Smith, Beth Chance
California Polytechnic State University, 1 Grand Avenue, San Luis Obispo, CA 93407

Abstract

Our cross-institutional study focuses on a particular component of intrinsic motivation in students' learning of introductory statistics: *curiosity*. We first piloted measures of students' curiosity, ranging from using the *Curiosity and Exploration Inventory-II* pre/post to collecting a series of "I wonder" open-ended responses throughout the term. We describe our data collection processes, provide preliminary example results to help assess the viability of the plan, and discuss lessons learned before fuller implementation in the coming school year.

Key Words: Statistics education, Intrinsic motivation, Learning, Student engagement, Teaching environment

1. Introduction

How students learn Statistics and how instructors can effectively help them has been a focal point in statistics education research over the past few decades (e.g., Carver et al., 2016; Garfield, 1995; Garfield & Ben-Zvi, 2007). While earlier studies focused on different teaching approaches (e.g., Simon et al., 1976; Federer, 1978), cognitive challenges and misconceptions (e.g., Brewer, 1985; Garfield and Ahlgren, 1988), and students' attitudes (e.g., Pavlick, 1975; Gal and Ginsburg, 1994), recent research has shifted toward understanding the motivational aspects of learning statistics, such as interest (e.g., Sproesser, 2016), self-efficacy (e.g., Finney and Schraw, 2003), and intrinsic motivation (e.g., Dun, 2014). For example, "information gap theory" suggests that students are naturally curious about missing information and motivated to fill these gaps (Loewenstein, 1998). In this multi-year, multi-institutional study, we aim to explore curiosity as part of intrinsic motivation, recognizing its potential to enhance students' learning (Pluck and Johnson, 2011).

Curiosity, or the desire to acquire knowledge, is integral to learning environments that actively engage students when teachers can use specific techniques to evoke curiosity, enriching the learning atmosphere (Schmitt and Lahroodi, 2008). Kashdan et al. (2009) conceptualize curiosity in undergraduates as comprising two components: (1) the motivation to seek new knowledge and experiences and (2) an openness to novelty, uncertainty, and unpredictability. Our study adopts a dual approach to understanding curiosity in the context of statistics education, aiming to clarify students' comprehension of statistics and their inclination to delve further into the subject.

During year 0 of this project (IRB #2024-210-CP), we developed a rubric to categorize responses in terms of the types of curiosity (e.g., concepts vs. contexts). Exploring these distributions across days, courses, and institutions will allow us to potentially identify which statistical concepts (inference, modeling, probability etc.), which classroom activities (investigation, simulation, direct instruction etc.), and which data contexts (e.g., sports, climate change, animals, self-care) spark their curiosity.

2. Methodology

2.1 Instruments Used

We used three main instruments in our project: a survey measuring general curiosity which we administered as a pre and end-of-course survey; a midterm student survey targeting perceived

changes in curiosity; and “I wonder” questions, identifying what students were most curious about from a particular class period/week of the course.

The pre/end-of-course survey (Kashdan et al., 2009) consists of ten questions geared toward assessing students’ predilection for “embracing” — “[the] willingness to ‘embrace’ the novel, uncertain, and unpredictable nature of everyday life” and “stretching” — “actively seeking opportunities for new information and experiences.” Students were asked to complete this survey (approximately 10 min) at the start and end of the course to measure baseline and changes in students’ general curiosity. This survey was administered, along with a consent form for the project, in Microsoft Forms.

The mid-term survey consisted of two questions: (1) Did your ‘curiosity’ about Probability or Statistics increase during this course? Please cite 1-2 examples where you felt more curious/what made you curious. (2) How do you feel your curiosity impacted your engagement in the course / ability to understand the material? These were open-ended questions administered in Canvas.

The “I wonder” questions were administered as “graded surveys” in Canvas (automatic credit for completion). Students were asked to submit the I wonder question before they left class or, if they did not attend class that day, after they had engaged with the course material for the corresponding class period (e.g., read the notes, watched a video). These surveys were set up in the Canvas calendar to remind students to submit their response before the next class period. These questions were posed 1-4 times/week (per instructor discretion).

2.2 Data Collection

All of the university courses were 10-week quarter courses. In addition, data was collected in a high school statistics class over a 10-week period. At Cal Poly, introductory students in the GE courses are separated by home major; the differences between courses allows for the exploration of curiosity within different academic contexts.

Table 1: Details about courses from which data were collected				
Class	Majors	School	Credit	I wonder question frequency
STAT 217 (2 instructors, Winter, Spring)	Social sciences	Cal Poly	Part of 10% course participation	Daily/weekly
STAT 251 (Winter, Spring)	Business	Cal Poly	Extra credit (2%)	Weekly
STAT 301 (2 instructors, Winter)	Statistics, Mathematics, and Economics	Cal Poly	Part of 10% course participation	Daily/weekly
PSTAT 10 (Winter)	Statistics, Data Science, and CS	UCSB	5% of overall grade	Daily
PSTAT 120B (Winter)	Statistics, Data Science, and CS	UCSB	5% of overall grade	Daily
STAT 311 (Spring)	General education	University of Washington	No course credit	Weekly

STAT 342 (Winter)	Statistics	University of Washington	No course credit	Weekly
Introductory Honors (AP) Statistics	High school	Lawrenceville School, NJ	Included in 5% participation score	Weekly
Honors Calculus-based Prob and Stats	High school	Lawrenceville School, NJ	Included in 5% participation score	Weekly

2.3 Rubric Generation

Using inductive coding (Thomas, 2006), we developed the rubric within a multi-institution collaboration (see Acknowledgments); rather than starting with a predetermined framework, we reviewed a large sample of student responses to identify recurring themes and indicators of curiosity. After iterating through many cycles of coding, discussions, and refinement, these patterns formed the initial structure of the rubric. As more data was analyzed, the rubric continued to evolve with more dimensions of question types and curiosity being recognized. This process ensured that the rubric would continue to represent curiosity as it was being observed in the “I wonder” questions data. Table 2 shows the current version of the rubric being used for ongoing coding and analysis.

Table 2: Simplified rubric used for coding responses (colors continued in plots)

<i>Question Type</i>	<i>Description</i>
0. No “I Wonder” question	Students were given the option to indicate or describe that they didn't have any questions that day
1. Unrelated to recent statistical content/ contexts	1a. Course/logistics 1b. Life/personal/pop culture 1c. Own or others' understanding of statistics 1d. Performance/how to learn/anxiety
2. Clarification questions about statistical/ technology concepts	2a. Clarification on current material (concept, equation, surface level, general) 2b. Technology 2c. Communication/Interpretation;
3. Extension questions about statistical/ technology context	3a. Further exploration/next step 3b. Extend and connect (e.g. prior course) 3c. History of techniques
4. Real world practical use	How ideas from course can be applied to own discipline/interests
5. Questions about context	4a. From course 4b. Own research 4c. General research practices

3. Exploratory Analyses

In this section, we describe the data we collected in year 0 and provide preliminary analyses to illustrate what we hope to learn from the larger study.

3.1 Data Context

Below we highlight example analyses with our preliminary data from three Cal Poly introductory statistics courses, STAT 217 (social science), STAT 251 (business), and STAT 301 (math, econ, and statistics). All three are required classes for their respective (groups of) majors, and were taught in Winter or Spring by three different professors. We collected data from 25 students in one

section of STAT 217, 117 students across three sections of STAT 251, and 130 across four sections of Stat 301. A few programs which require STAT 217 are: BS Anthropology and Geography, BA Sociology, and BA Political Science. STAT 251 is mandated by at least BS Business Administration and BS Industrial Technology and Packaging. STAT 217 and 251 fulfill a general education requirement; STAT 301 has a calculus co-requisite.

3.2 General Curiosity

Figure 1 shows results from the pre-course general curiosity survey (Kashdan et al., 2009) to see whether there were any substantial pre-course differences in curiosity between the groups. Focusing on spring data, we note an apparent lack of any strong difference between the students' pre-course "embracing" curiosity, as their violin plots show a similar enough shape and center. However, looking at the appropriate "stretching" violin plots, we could note that STAT 217 and STAT 301 students' "stretching" curiosity seems to be higher than that of STAT 251 students.

Figure 1: Pre-course curiosity levels from students in multiple courses across two dimensions of five questions each.

Across the four courses (merged across sections/professors in the same quarter), internal consistency in the pre-course survey varied. Stretching reliability tended to be weak, with embracing reliability marginally better. Total consistency was approximately acceptable for the two winter courses and marginal in the two spring courses. Our estimates are all below the benchmarks in Kashdan et al. (2009), indicating weaker reliability in these data.

Table 3: Cronbach α for CEI-II				
Class	n	α (Stretching) [95% CI]	α (Embracing) [95% CI]	α (Total) [95% CI]
STAT 251 Winter	126	0.652 [0.558, 0.747]	0.632 [0.524, 0.723]	0.787 [0.733, 0.842]
STAT 301 Winter	130	0.675 [0.588, 0.763]	0.784 [0.726, 0.843]	0.816 [0.770, 0.862]
STAT 217	25	0.676	0.701	0.676

Spring		[0.473, 0.879]	[0.517, 0.885]	[0.484, 0.868]
STAT 251 Spring	117	0.570 [0.445, 0.695]	0.533 [0.402, 0.664]	0.699 [0.618, 0.780]

3.3 Statistical Curiosity

Turning now towards Statistical curiosity, we coded all the “I Wonder” responses from STAT 251 to see whether there were any patterns in the types of questions being asked. These responses are categorized in accordance with Table 2 above. We can see in Figure 2 that the types of questions students asked did seem to change over the course of the term. For example, in week 5 there was an increase in “clarifying statistical concepts” (light blue; “What is a p-value?”)—in tandem with an upcoming exam. Similarly, note the steady increase in “course logistics/performance” questions (orange; “What will be on the final?”) from weeks 8 to 9—likely due to heightened anxiety surrounding the final exam, administered after week 10.

Throughout the term we can see a substantial proportion of students’ questions are clarifying statistical concepts questions (light blue). This is not surprising and reflects the introductory nature of the course. What is more interesting is the prevalence of questions about statistics in the real world (darkest blue)—we noted that students frequently wondered about how the topics they were learning could be applicable to their future jobs. In particular, with the business-oriented majors, we frequently identified students asking how they could use probability to play the stock market, or how to use a *t*-test in a business or human resources setting. We also coded a random sample of responses from STAT 217, which consists of a larger diversity of majors, and found this type of question to occur less frequently. We posit that the more homogenous class audience in STAT 251 makes it easier to find engaging contexts which appeal to the class on a whole. In courses covering a more disparate set of majors, it may be harder to find contexts which connect to all students.

We also note that the overall response rate decreased over the term, but not to an alarming degree. We feel tying participation to a small incentive was useful, as well as integrating reminders in the course and the course management system. Future iterations could involve more instructor feedback to the students’ questions during the term to ensure students their voices are being heard and responded to (e.g., minute papers, Angelo & Cross, 1993).

Figure 2: The types of questions Stat 251 students asked varied per week. Response rates (along the top) were relatively high, though decreasing, throughout the term. Students tended to ask more clarifying and logistics/performance questions around exams (week 5 and after week 10).

We also wanted to explore the association between innate curiosity and the “I Wonder” responses. Using the pre-course curiosity levels, we binned students’ scores into three groups representing the inherent general curiosity levels of students coming into the course. Looking at the types of questions asked per group, we can then see some interesting patterns; we can see that students with a higher level of baseline curiosity tended to ask more questions about contexts (coral) and fewer about course logistics (orange). We can also see that high pre-curiosity students tended to ask fewer questions overall (grey). The response rate didn’t differ drastically by pre-course curiosity level.

Figure 3: Students with higher levels of baseline curiosity tended to ask more questions about contexts and fewer about course logistics (and fewer questions overall).

4. Conclusions

Based on our year 0 results, we think there is an underlying construct of 'statistical curiosity' that can be measured and explored, and that students enter their introductory statistics courses with potentially different levels of innate curiosity. The series of "I wonder" questions, with sufficient structure and incentive, is useful in capturing different types of student curiosity from course logistics to clarification on the material to extensions to their current knowledge. In particular, students who ask extension/application-type questions seem to be engaging with the material at a level which isn't strictly necessary in order to score well in class, thus satisfying our definition of curiosity as the desire to acquire knowledge. Kashdan et al. (2009) conceptualize curiosity in undergraduates as comprising two components: (1) the motivation to seek new knowledge and experiences and (2) an openness to novelty, uncertainty, and unpredictability. We further think that questions about contexts used in class also capture curiosity, but a different, non-statistical kind—closer to the “general curiosity” measured in the pre and post-course survey. This is further substantiated by Figure 3 where we can see that STAT 251 students with high pre-curiosity levels seemed to ask more questions about context than the other two groups. We hope future exploration will also allow us to identify particular example contexts that heighten students' interest in the materials.

This year, we are collecting and coding additional data using our rubric, we hope to explore research questions such as:

- Are there student-level characteristics that predict students’ level of curiosity in introductory statistics?
- Are there course-level characteristics (e.g., content, contexts) that predict the type of questions students ask (e.g., clarification vs. further exploration)?

- Are students' levels of curiosity related to course performance?
- Can instructors' pedagogical choices and/or course design *evoke* students' curiosity?

We learned a number of lessons after our first period of data collection; chief among them is the importance of consolidating our data collection procedures to Canvas, a common learning management system. Moving to Canvas allowed us to set up automatic reminders to students to complete informed consent forms and surveys and restrict when surveys were available so students could not complete missing surveys from earlier time frames. This also allows us to immediately deidentify student data and match across informed consent by relying on their random Canvas ID. Building our tooling in Canvas also allows us to easily share pre-set up individual I wonder graded surveys with other instructors.

We also realized that, in order to answer our research questions this year, we need to collect more data from instructors about the contexts and content covered in lessons. This will allow us to measure whether specific contexts are more appealing to students. We will also encourage instructors to offer a smaller incentive (e.g., participation points), with option to opt out, to encourage student participation, among other opportunities. We did find requiring students to reflect on their learning and perspectives on the course to be beneficial as well.

Coding responses is very resource intensive, so we have been exploring a few pathways to reduce the time and effort required in manual coding. To that end, we are planning to explore students' accuracy in self-classifying their "I Wonder" questions. We are also considering the usage of ML models—viz. fine-tuning a model or effectively prompting off-the-shelf LLMs—to serve as a second reviewer for manual coding. Looking ahead, we plan to extend our analysis through stronger cross-institutional analyses—we would like to explore curiosity levels as they change over time within a course and between different courses.

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References

- Angelo, T. A., Cross, K. P. (1993). *Classroom Assessment Techniques*, 2nd ed. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass. 148-53
- Brewer, W. F. (1985). Some possible ways to help students overcome misconceptions in probability and statistics. In Proceedings of the *Seventh Annual Meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education*.
- Carver, R., Everson, M., Gabrosek, J., Horton, N., Lock, R., Mocko, M., Rossman, A., Velleman P., Wood, B., & Zigler, T. (2016). Guidelines for assessment and instruction in statistics education (GAISE) college report 2016. American Statistical Association.
- Dun, C. (2014). Exploring intrinsic motivation in undergraduate statistics education [Doctoral dissertation, University of South Florida].
- Federer, W. T. (1978). Teaching statistics: Suggestions for effective instruction. *The American Statistician*, 32(2), 67–70.
- Finney, S. J., & Schraw, G. (2003). Self-efficacy beliefs in college statistics courses. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 28(2), 161–186.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-476X\(02\)00015-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-476X(02)00015-2)

- Gal, I., & Ginsburg, L. (1994). The role of beliefs and attitudes in learning statistics: Toward an assessment framework. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 2(2).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10691898.1994.11910471>
- Garfield, J., & Ahlgren, A. (1988). Difficulties in learning basic concepts in probability and statistics: Implications for research. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 19(1), 44–63. <https://doi.org/10.2307/749110>
- Garfield, J. (1995). How students learn statistics. *International Statistical Review*, 63(1), 25-34.
- Garfield, J., & Ben-Zvi, D. (2007). How students learn statistics revisited: A current review of research on teaching and learning statistics. *International Statistical Review*, 73(3), 372-396.
- Kashdan, T. B., Gallagher, M. W., Silvia, P. J., Winterstein, B. P., Breen, W. E., Terhar, D., & Steger, M. F. (2009). The curiosity and exploration inventory–II: Development, factor structure, and psychometrics. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 43(6), 987–998.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2009.04.011>
- Loewenstein, G. (1998). The psychology of curiosity: A review and reinterpretation. *Psychological Bulletin*, 116(1), 75–98. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.116.1.75>
- Pavlick, R. A. (1975). A study of college students' attitudes toward statistics and their relationship to achievement [Doctoral dissertation, University of Cincinnati].
- Pluck, G., & Johnson, H. (2011). Stimulating curiosity to enhance learning. *Educational Psychology Review*, 23(4), 749–770. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-011-9179-0>
- Schmitt, F. F., & Lahroodi, R. (2008). The epistemic value of curiosity. *Educational Theory*, 58(2), 125–148. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-5446.2008.00281.x>
- Simon, J. L., Atkinson, G. B. J., & Shevokas, C. (1976). Teaching statistics: Testing some common assumptions. *The American Statistician*, 30(4), 197–204.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.1976.10479157>
- Sproesser, U., Engel, J., & Kuntze, S. (2016). Interest in statistics and its relationship to mathematical literacy and attitudes toward statistics. *Statistics Education Research Journal*, 15(2), 119–137.
- Thomas, D. R. (2006). A general inductive approach for analyzing qualitative evaluation data. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 27(2), 237-246. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098214005283748>